

DETECTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF CHANGES IN THE
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACES

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Changes in the physical state of fibre/matrix interfaces can be detected by internally reflecting a beam of light from the interfaces. In the case of glass fibre composites, if the refractive index of the matrix is less than that of the glass, the light-pipe characteristics of the fibres can be usefully exploited. For opaque fibres in a transparent matrix, the matrix is the transmitting medium. In both cases, interfacial changes are manifested by changes in transmitted intensity. Changes in transmission have been observed in composites of glass and of carbon fibres in matrices of polyester resin, epoxy resin and Portland cement during subjection of the composites to various mechanical and chemical treatments. In a wet environment, the occurrence of interfacial water and its freezing and thawing during subsequent temperature cycling are readily detected. So too is the progress of mechanical debonding during slow fibre pull-out tests. The value of optical transmitted intensity measurements as a sensor has been demonstrated by studies of the early stages of both the generation of osmotic pressure resulting from dissolution of water solubles located at the interface and the molecular orientation that occurs in the resin adjacent to totally embedded fibre ends during gross resin shrinkage. Assessments have also been made of the effectiveness of a silane coupling agent, and of the assumed hydrophobic qualities of carbon fibre and of the incidence of frost shattering.

1. Introduction

For aesthetic reasons, manufacturers usually try to match the refractive index of the resin to that of the glass fibre. To use the fibres as light-pipes, however, the refractive index of the glass must be greater than that of the surrounding medium; transmission along the fibres is by multiple internal reflections, the critical angle of incidence for which is $c = \sin^{-1}(\mu_{\text{resin}}/\mu_{\text{glass}})$. By carefully selecting the resin and glass compositions, it is possible to meet the light-pipe condition. The light is introduced (and removed) by refraction across the ends of the fibres and, taking this into account, it is found that the incident light needs to be aimed at an angle of less than $\sim 10^\circ$ to the fibre axis direction.* Since $\mu_{\text{glass}} \sim \mu_{\text{resin}} > \mu_{\text{water}} > \mu_{\text{air}}$, it is evident that smaller critical angles will be associated with air - or water-filled interfacial gaps. Consequently, by aiming the incident beam at a slightly larger angle than 10° to the fibre axis direction, so that the condition for total internal reflection by a glass/resin interface is not met, the subsequent occurrence of debonding should be detected as enhanced transmission resulting from total internal reflection.

In practice, the expected increase in transmitted intensity is not observed. Changes in the reflectivity of glass fibres in polyester resin matrices are observed during mechanical pull-out and during exposure to wet environments (1) but these changes are always reductions in transmitted intensity. The first part of the present paper examines these observations in the light of phenomena which are simultaneously taking place within the resin.

To use the reflection of light as a tool for detecting interfacial changes in carbon fibre/resin composites, it is necessary to reverse the roles played by the fibre and matrix materials. The matrix is now the transmission medium and due regard has to be paid to changes in the transmitting properties of the resin itself. Since there is no possibility of transmission by the carbon, there is more flexibility in the choice of angle of incidence. By making this angle larger than the critical angle for resin to air (resin to water in the case of composites exposed to water), the appearance of air (or water) at the interface should produce

* To increase the number of reflections and hence amplify the effects of interfacial changes, larger glancing angles are required. These can be employed if the resin is rendered opaque by introducing a suitable pigment during preparation of the sample.

total internal reflection and hence an increase in transmitted intensity. The latter part of this paper describes experiments which demonstrate this expected increase in transmission. The composites used are carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resins and interpretation of the results reveals the identities of several mechanisms of water damage in epoxy resins as well as an example of apparently hydrophilic behaviour of carbon fibre.

2. Materials

All of the specimens investigated here were prepared in our own laboratory using the following commercial grades of resins and fibres, kindly supplied by U.K. manufacturers.

(a) An ortho-phthalic polyester resin coded BP 868, obtained from BIP Chemicals Ltd., Olbury, Worcestershire. This resin contains methylmethacrylate monomer, which enhances its translucence, and styrene, as plasticiser. The catalyst, a methyl ethyl ketone peroxide, and the accelerator, cobalt naphthalenate, were also supplied by BIP chemicals. The proportions of catalyst (2 vol.%) and accelerator (0.5 vol.%) and the curing procedure (24h. in air at 20C followed by 24h. in air at 60 C) were as recommended by the manufacturer. The refractive index of the fully cured resin is 1.55.

(b) "Araldite" epoxy resin MY 750 (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A), hardener HY 917 (methyltetrahydrophthalic anhydride), and accelerator DY 062 (triethylammonium phenate), all supplied by Ciba-Geigy (U.K.) Ltd., Duxford, Cambridgeshire. Following the manufacturers recommendations, mixes consisting of 100 : 85 : 2 parts by weight of resin, hardener and accelerator were gelled for 2h. at 100 C and then cured for 4h. at 150 C. The refractive index of the fully cured resin is 1.57.

(c) 15 μ m diameter zirconia containing glass fibre supplied by Fibreglass Ltd., St. Helens, Lancs., and having a refractive index of 1.61.

(d) 9 μ m diameter carbon fibre supplied by Courtauld's Ltd., Coventry, Warwickshire and designated type B.

3. Method

The broad aim of this research programme is to identify the physical mechanisms associated with measured changes in optical transmission. Most of the measurements reported here were made during accelerated weathering tests and, for these results to be relevant to short fibre composites, it was necessary to make sure that the only access of water to the fibres is by diffusion through the resin. The specimen shape adopted is sketched in figure 1. It is clamped in a miniature hot water tank, with its shoulders each compressing an "O" ring against the periphery of a hole through which the fibres protrude, see

figure 2. The specimen length is 3cm and the estimated fibre

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

content is ~ 2000 for the $15\mu\text{m}$ diameter glass fibres and $> 10,000$ for the $9\mu\text{m}$ diameter carbon fibres. Details of the specimen casting technique and of the fibre end polishing procedure are given in reference (1).

The fibres are illuminated by light from a helium neon laser and the transmitted intensity is measured using a photocell and amplifier. In the early tests on glass fibre/polyester resin composites, reported in section 4, a photovoltaic selenium photocell was used as part of a small transistor amplifier but, in subsequent experiments, this was replaced by a photoresistive cadmium sulphide photocell used as the input resistor for an operational amplifier integrated circuit. The details are given in figure 3. With this revised circuit, an improved stabilisation against temperature changes has been obtained. The optical bench also incorporates a facility for splitting the incident beam so that the long-term stability of the light source can be checked with a second photo cell.

4. Glass fibre reinforced polyester resin

One successful application of the light pipe technique has been the study of water damage in GRP. Figure 4 illustrates the fall in transmitted intensity, expressed as a fraction of the initial transmitted intensity, during continuous exposure to water at 95C . The decrease is attributed to increased dispersion at the interface resulting from etching of the fibre surfaces. After

$$R_2 = K \frac{1}{L}^\gamma, \quad \gamma \sim 1$$

$L \propto$ illumination

K, γ are constants

$$V_{out} = V_{ref} \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

Therefore V_{out} increases with increasing L .

R_1 : 10 M Ω feedback

R_2 : photocell (30 M Ω in dark)

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

prolonged exposure, the etching becomes very pronounced and is easily resolved by scanning electron microscopy of fibres extracted from the composite, see figure 5. This etching is believed to be due to dissolution of the water soluble constituents (Na_2O , K_2O) of the glass fibre (2). In the case of short fibre composites, total debonding by this mechanism is succeeded by propagation into the resin of lens-shaped cracks oriented

perpendicular to the fibre. Figure 6 shows one surface of such a lens crack, revealed by fracturing the whole composite. These

Fig. 5. Scanning electron micrograph of "E" glass fibre extracted from composite after 400h. in boiling water (2).

Fig. 6. Scanning electron micrograph of a fibre and associated indentation crack.

Fig. 7. Linear Dimensional Changes of Resin. ●, Post-cure in Air at 100°C; ▲, Water Immersion at 60°C; ■, 3-day Post-cure in Air at 100°C Followed by Immersion in Boiling Water.

cracks are a consequence of the resin shrinkage which accompanies water uptake, see figure 7. Debonding is accompanied by a large build-up of the compressive stress exerted across the fibre ends. Although partially relieved by molecular orientation

(3), the compression in the resin eventually causes the nucleation of cone-cracks.

5. Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin

To make use of changes in the optical reflectivity of resin/carbon fibre interfaces as a sensor of debonding, it is necessary to use the matrix as the transmission medium. In the specimens examined here, the fibres are strictly aligned parallel to the axis and, with the incident beam aimed at a glancing angle of less than 30° to the axis, a large fraction of the light is absorbed by the fibres. Since the critical angle from epoxy resin to water is $\sim 60^\circ$, the appearance of interfacial water is expected to produce total internal reflection and hence should be detected as an increase in transmitted intensity. Figure 8 shows that, for exposure to distilled water maintained at 95°C , a significant concentration of diffused water is collected at the resin/fibre

Fig. 8

interfaces after 550h. This implies a water diffusion coefficient of perhaps $\sim 10^{-7} \text{ g. cm.}^{-1} \text{ s.}^{-1}$. It also presumably implies the presence at the interface of solute since, otherwise, there would be no thermodynamic driving force to cause precipitation of diffused water. Carbon is normally hydrophobic and a priori one might have expected diffused water to avoid diffusion towards the fibres. In the case of glass fibre composites, see section 4, it was suggested that the K_2O plus Na_2O content of the glass is responsible for precipitation of diffused water. It may be that carbon fibres also contain inorganic water solubles, perhaps

introduced during a drying process. On the other hand, the possible presence of organic water soluble inclusions cannot be ruled out.

The detection of water precipitation at carbon fibre/resin interfaces raises the possibility of "wicking". The rate of water uptake in glass-fibre composites is considerably enhanced by the presence of fibres which penetrate the exposed external surface and this is usually attributed to capillary tube behaviour of interfacial gaps. Now if, due to the presence of soluble impurities, the surface of a carbon fibre is able to attract water (or, for that matter, any other polar solvent), dissolution of the same impurities may provide a mechanism for "wicking". To investigate this possibility, specimens were cast with the riser of the casting mould starved of resin. The pipe so introduced into one of the resin shoulders, see figure 1, was then used to give direct access to the fibres. That water is immediately accepted by the interface is demonstrated by the observed very rapid rise in intensity of the emergent beam.

Since the matrix is used as transmission medium for these experiments, water degradation of the resin itself takes an added importance when trying to interpret the data obtained. Figures 9 and 10 respectively show the changes in linear

Fig. 9

dimensions and the changes in weight, during water exposure of the fully cured epoxy resin containing no fibres. The net effect is a progressively decreasing density which is tentatively

Fig. 10

attributed to the leaching out of low molecular weight material such as might arise from insufficient mixing. This would introduce resin- or hardener-enriched regions, both of which would be susceptible to hydrolysis via epoxy, hydroxyl or ether linkages. Inhomogeneous regions can also be produced by self-diffusion of hardener towards reactive centres or as a consequence of convection resulting from the large heat of reaction. Chemical analyses of water used in water exposure experiments together with details of the proposed leaching mechanism will be published elsewhere.

The first observable resin damage in slabs 3.2mm thick is the appearance of lens-shaped internal cracks after 200h. exposure to boiling water. Examination between crossed polars reveals the presence of strain in the resin surrounding each lens, see figure 11(a). Scanning electron microscopy of lens surfaces exposed by fracturing the bulk material demonstrates that, as in the case for polyester resins (section 4), the lens cracks are associated with solid deposits, figure 11(b). Taken together, these two observations suggest that the lens cracks are identical to those seen in polyester resins (4) and ought, therefore, to be attributed to the generation of pockets of pressure. A mechanism for the simultaneous creation of the biaxial compression required in order to convert pockets of pressure into regions of tension

Fig. 11(a) Optical micrograph of lens crack 2, 15mm in diameter. 369h. 100 C.

Fig. 11(b) Scanning electron micrograph showing deposits on a lens crack surface. Marker = 1 μ m. 1200 h. 100C.

capable of propagating cracks is not obvious. The second stage of observable damage, namely the formation of bubbles in the surface layers, may, however, provide the answer.

Figure 12(a) shows the appearance of these bubbles after 950h.

Fig. 12(a) Denuded zone surrounding a lens crack. Marker=100 μ m. 954h. 100C.

Fig. 12(b) Air bubbles developing inside water-filled bubbles. Marker=100 μ m. 836h. 100C.

Fig. 13(a) 2mm. diameter lens crack sprouting "wormholes". 485h. 100C.

Fig. 13(b),(c) Optical micrographs showing appearance of wormholes at different levels of focus. Marker = 100 μ m. 954h. 100C.

Fig. 13(c)

Fig. 14 Black deposits within lens crack and adjoining "wormholes". Marker = 100 μ m. 836h. 100C.

exposure to boiling water. Note that the resin adjacent to the lens crack is denuded of bubbles, as might be expected if the resin thereabouts is in a state of compression due to the presence of pressure within the lens. Examination between crossed polars fails to detect any strain associated with the bubbles. That they are water filled is evident from the appearance within them of air bubbles during drying out on the microscope stage, see figure 12(b). If the leaching out of low molecular weight material is accommodated by bubble formation, the weight loss shown in figure 10 may be associated with shrinkage in the surface layers. The implied tension in the surface layers could, in turn, be the origin of the internal compression with which pockets of pressure must interact in order to provide the regions of tension required for internal fractures.

Continuation of the exposure to boiling water causes "wormholes" to nucleate from lens cracks. Two such defects can be seen growing from the same lens in figure 13(a). Through focus examination of a wormhole, figure 13(b) and (c), reveals a sharply defined axis which threads a row of bubbles. Wormholes are often seen to contain a particle of dark contrast, figure 14. Such particles may well be catalysts for the observed very rapid attack of the resin by the solution contained inside the parent lens crack.

Prolonged (> 800h.) boiling water exposure results in the deposition of tarry products on the external surface.

Each of the resin defects described above is likely to disperse any light which falls upon it. Hence, it is concluded that none of the increase in transmitted intensity observed during water uptake can be attributed to these forms of damage; it must all be due to enhanced reflection by the resin/fibre interfaces.

References

1. P. Leach and K.H.G. Ashbee, *Composites* (1974) 5, 67-72
2. K.H.G. Ashbee and R.C. Wyatt, *Proc. Roy. Soc.* (1969) A312, 553-564
3. K.H.G. Ashbee, 5th Intl. Materials Symposium, edited by G. Thomas, R.M. Fulrath and R.M. Fisher, Univ. of Calif. Press (1972) 1205-1222
4. K.H.G. Ashbee, F.C. Frank and R.C. Wyatt, *Proc. Roy. Soc.* (1967) A300, 415-419